

ANALYSIS OF LEGAL ISSUES IN THE TRADE SECTOR DURING UZBEKISTAN'S TRANSITION TO A MARKET ECONOMY: A REVIEW OF SOURCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19912061>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th April 2026

Accepted: 26th April 2026

Online: 28th April 2026

KEYWORDS

trade sector, socio-economic processes, historical approach, market relations, archival sources, statistical data, independence period, economic reforms

ABSTRACT

This article examines socio-economic processes in the trade sector from a historical perspective. It explores the formation and development stages of trade relations and their role in the economic life of society. Based on archival documents, statistical data, and periodical sources, the study analyzes transformations in the trade system and their social implications. Particular attention is paid to the reinterpretation of these processes during the independence period using new methodological approaches.

During the years of independence, special attention was paid to the objective and scientific study of national history, and the ideological restrictions that existed in the previous period were eliminated. As a result, the opportunity to reassess the content and essence of socio-economic processes in the field of trade and to analyze them objectively based on sources expanded. In particular, the widespread introduction of archival documents, statistical data, and periodical press materials brought scientific research in this area to a new level.

From this point of view, the study of socio-economic processes in the field of trade based on a historical approach is of great importance not only in identifying trends in economic development, but also in shedding light on the characteristics of social changes in society, the standard of living of the population, and the formation of market relations. This issue is especially relevant in analyzing the changes that occurred during the transition from the administrative-command system formed during the Soviet era to a market economy.

Documents on the trade-related activities of these organizations from the funds of various ministries, concerns, associations and other organizations stored in the National Archives of Uzbekistan are studied, and the conclusions obtained as a result of the research are brought into scientific circulation. This creates an opportunity to form and describe the partial aspect of the science of history, that is, the history of trade from a modern point of view, based on new approaches. In particular, information is collected on the state policy on trade and the formation of its legal framework, the state of the industry, problems, the organization of the trade process, the formation of types of trade goods and the dynamics of their production.

Uzbekistan has developed a unique and extensive experience in the production and export of agricultural products. Information on this area can be collected using the documents of the Uzbek State Joint-Stock Association “Uzgoskhlopkopromsbyt” for the processing of raw cotton and the sale of cotton products, stored in the M-8 fund of the State Archives of Uzbekistan, the Association of Foreign Economic Activities of Enterprises and Organizations of the State Concern for Agricultural Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the M-9 fund, the Association of Poultry Production Enterprises “Uzparrandasanoat” under the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the M-16 fund, the Holding Company “Uzmevasabzavotuzumsanoat-Holding” in the M-25 fund, the State Joint-Stock Association “Uzgoshtsutsanoat” in the M-82 fund, the Republican Production Association “Uzgoshtsutsanoat” under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the M-83 fund, and the Republican Association “Uzbekipagi” in the M-52 fund. With the help of the information in these documents, the agricultural-related aspects of Uzbek trade aspects are analyzed, in particular, the processes related to cotton cultivation and the production and sale of products from it, the activities of enterprises producing poultry products that are in demand in domestic and foreign trade, the production and sale of fruit and vegetable products, meat and dairy products are clarified. Therefore, the documents stored in these funds serve as an important source in the analysis of Uzbekistan's trade during the period of independence.

List 1, volume 89 of the M-142 fund of the National Archives of Uzbekistan (State Grain Inspectorate under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan) provides information on the problems of production and sale of agricultural products, export and import. The documents of the volume indicate that in 2008 the country's gross domestic product grew by 9 percent compared to the previous year. The volume of industrial production increased by 12.7 percent. It is indicated that the production of agricultural products increased by 4.5 percent. Retail trade amounted to 17.2 percent.

Or in the 74th volume of this fund, grain and grain product production enterprises are listed by region. For example, the volume notes that in 2008, 30,580 tons of grain were produced and sold in Namangan region, and 80,000 tons in Kashkadarya region. At the same time, 53.5 thousand tons of grain were imported from abroad in the same year.

In the 100th volume of the 1st list of the M-142 fund, minutes of the meetings of the State Grain Inspectorate on the production, transportation, import, sale of flour and grain products in 2010-2011, etc. are presented. In the 101st volume of this fund, information is provided on grain production by enterprises and organizations, grain volume, quality, quantitative volume, grain purchase from farmers.

Analysis of available sources indicates that the country's major industries are not ready for this economic process, characterized by the fact that the domestic market prices of the products they produce are higher than the external market prices.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the International Monetary Fund, the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the International Development Association, the International Finance Corporation, the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency", among other influential international organizations, became the legal basis for our country to become

an equal member of the IMF. On April 27, 1992, Uzbekistan was admitted to the IMF and its representative office was opened in Tashkent.

On March 18, 1998, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures to deepen cooperation with the International Monetary Fund", and in 2002 a Memorandum was signed between the Government of Uzbekistan and the IMF. In June 2003, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Central Bank developed an "Action Plan for the Free Conversion of the National Currency in Current International Transactions" and submitted it to the IMF. On October 15, 2003, the Republic of Uzbekistan signed Article 8 of the IMF Agreement and accepted the obligation to ensure the free conversion of the national currency, the soum, into foreign currencies in current international transactions. These information documents are also of great importance in the study of the subject.

World Bank documents such as the "Assessment Report (DAR BCP)" (XVF/World Bank), "IOSCO ROSC (Summary)" (XVF), "Detailed Assessment Report (DAR IOSCO) (IMF)", "Detailed Assessment Commentary (DAO IAIS)" (World Bank), "AML/CFT Technical Note (IMF)", "Technical Note on Macroprudential Analysis and Policy Module (IMF)", "Technical Note on Corporate Governance and State-Owned Banks Module (World Bank)", "Technical Note on Financial Integration Module (World Bank)", "Technical Note on Financial Market Infrastructure and Central Counterparty Module (World Bank)" also serve to supplement the subject literature

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